

Case Report: A Case of Fetal Anemia

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Citation: Saira Waheed, Mehreen Altaf. Case Report: A Case of Fetal Anemia. *Int Clin Med Case Rep Jour.* 2023;2(17):1-3.

Received Date: 18 November, 2023; **Accepted Date:** 23 November, 2023; **Published Date:** 27 November, 2023

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INTRODUCTION

A case of severe Fetal Anemia secondary to Rhesus isoimmunisation at 31 weeks is discussed which required immediate delivery of the Fetus due to abnormal CTG trace and impending stillbirth. The patient was under surveillance with a tertiary Fetal medicine centre on a fortnightly basis and was followed up with blood tests and middle cerebral artery dopplers scans. Before presenting to our unit, there was a history of reduced Fetal movements for three days in this patient.

Keywords: Fetal Anemia; Pregnancy; Fetal medicine

CASE REPORT

A 41 years old, G4P3 was presented at 31 weeks of pregnancy. She was Rhesus negative with Anti- D and Anti- C antibodies. Her Anti-D titres in the beginning of pregnancy were 14. She was under the Fetal medicine unit and was closely followed up 1-2 weekly Middle Cerebral artery (MCA) Dopplers from 20 weeks of pregnancy. Her MCA Doppler was in the normal range till 28 weeks of pregnancy but became more than 1.5 MoM at 28 weeks when she was referred to (Fetal medicine unit) FMU at a tertiary centre for intra-uterine transfusion.

She had an intra-uterine transfusion performed at 29 weeks and was planned for a second transfusion at 31+1 weeks. She has had a follow up scan done at the Fetal Medicine unit at tertiary centre at 30+6 weeks which showed a well grown baby weighing 1.8 Kgs with MCA PSV > 2MoM (104 -111cms/s) with small amount of ascites. She reported (Reduced fetal movements) RFM on that day. As a part of monitoring, she had a (computerized)CTG done which met the Dawes Redmann Criteria (DRC.) But the cCTG had a BR of 157/min with some sinusoidal features. The patient was advised to go home and return after 2 days for her planned intrauterine transfusion.

She attended our ANDU the next day at 31 weeks with absent fetal movements. CCTG was immediately commenced, and a sinusoidal pattern was noted suggestive of fetal anemia. Fetal Medicine centre at tertiary centre was contacted to explore the possibility of urgent intra-uterine transfusion. However, this did not seem possible and since the baby was at high risk of impending stillbirth due to severe fetal anemia, a decision was

made for a Category 1 caesarean section. A dose of antenatal corticosteroid and loading dose of Magnesium Sulphate was given prior to caesarean section. Transfusion was contacted for cross match as mother had antibodies. Paediatricians were informed to attend caesarean section and prepare for post-delivery transfusion of the baby.

C section was uneventful. Baby was born extremely pale, was not maintaining saturation, and was intubated. Baby's Haemoglobin was 35 at birth. Baby was transfused post-delivery and was transferred to tertiary centre for further management.

DISCUSSION

Fetal anemia is a relatively uncommon but dangerous condition. The most frequent cause is immune-related and involves red blood cell (RBC) alloimmunization. It happens due to sensitization of the mother to antigens on fetal RBCs derived from the father [1]. The most common antigens causing severe anemia is anti D and anti-cell antibodies [2]. High risk pregnancies are identified by a previous history of hemolytic disease of newborn or identification of antibodies on routine screening of blood [3]. Initial management is to identify paternal red cell rhesus status [4]. The fetal Rh genotype can now be determined non-invasively by measuring maternal cell free fetal DNA [5]. In pregnancies-effected by Rh antigens serial titre levels are performed every 4 weeks until 28 weeks then every 2 weeks afterwards [6].

The haemoglobin of a fetus increase gradually throughout pregnancy, classification of anemia is on the basis of the degree of Hb deviation from the mean for gestational age [7] or on multiples of the median (MoM)1 for Gestational age into mild (Hb deviation < 20 /dl), moderate (20-70 g/dl) or severe (>70g/dl) deviation [8]. Hydrops, a severe complication usually develops when the Hb deficit is > 70 g/L or the absolute Hb value is < 50 g/L [9].

The fetus, which is affected by hemolytic disease of newborn, will show signs of hydrops. The early signs of a hydroptic fetus can be ascites by ultrasound [10].

High-resolution ultrasound is now a new development in the management of fetal anemia which enables precise, non-invasive screening by measuring the middle cerebral artery peak systolic velocity (MCA-PSV) compared to the previous invasive methods of amniocentesis [11]. Advancements like intrauterine transfusions have now increased the survival rates to about 90 percent [12]. Intrauterine transfusions can now reverse changes of early hydrops and such Fetuses are then followed by weekly middle cerebral artery dopplers. [13].

Measurement of the peak MCA Doppler can begin as early as 18 weeks but more commonly is initiated at approximately 24 weeks

Obtaining a Middle Cerebral Artery Peak Systolic Velocity

NON INVASIVE DETECTION OF FETAL ANEMIA

CONCLUSION

This was a case of severe fetal anemia secondary to Rh isoimmunisation.

The lady was correctly being managed at a FM unit in a tertiary centre.

When she attended the FM unit at tertiary centre, she did report RFM since 2-3 days. Her MCA PSV was > 2 MoM at the time with small amount of ascites. Her CCTG did not look visually normal, though it did meet the criteria. Hence Ascites is a sign of early developing hydrops, such cases should be considered for intrauterine transfusion.

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